

Research Article

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The role of financial knowledge in enhancing financial product utilization among youth and women small-medium enterprises in Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities, Southwestern Uganda

Faustino Byanyima Byanyima¹, Willy Rwamparaji Kagarura², Ezra Francis Munyambonera³, Boaz Nabimanya⁴, Shine Arineitwe⁵, David Agaba⁶, Diana Nkamusiima⁷, Tonatus Agaba⁸, Donisian Hategyekimana⁹

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7&8}Department of Economics and Statistics, Faculty of Economics and Management Sciences, Kabale University, Uganda

⁹Department of Social Work, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Kabale University, Uganda

*Corresponding author: bnabimanya@kab.ac.ug

Abstract: While financial knowledge is gaining traction as an important enabler of quality financial inclusion, youth- and women-owned SMEs in emerging markets tend to underutilize the financial products available to them. The current study aims to investigate the relationship between financial knowledge and financial product utilization among youth- and women-owned SMEs in Southwestern Uganda, with a particular focus on Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities. The study utilized a cross-sectional, correlational research design, and primary data were collected from 395 SME owners and managers using a structured questionnaire. Financial knowledge was assessed based on indicators such as loan management, risk assessment, interest calculation, and inflation awareness. Financial product utilization was measured based on indicators such as savings accounts, mobile money, ATMs, bank transfers, bank loans, and SACCO services. The analysis was done using SPSS software. Principal component analysis was used to construct a financial product utilization index, while Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation was used to test the hypotheses. The results showed a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between financial knowledge and financial product utilization. SMEs with higher levels of financial knowledge were more likely to access and use formal financial products, especially credit and digital financial services, in a responsible manner. The study offers empirical evidence from the Ugandan SME context and highlights the importance of targeted financial literacy interventions as a complement to financial access efforts. Policy implications include integrating financial education components into SME support programs with a specific focus on women and youth entrepreneurs.

Keywords – Financial knowledge, Financial product utilization, Small and medium enterprises, Youth and women entrepreneurs, Uganda

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial knowledge has been recognized as an important driver of financial inclusion in developing countries (Alqam & Hamshari, 2024; Showkat et al., 2025). Financial knowledge refers to an individual's ability to understand and use financial concepts to make financial decisions for themselves or their businesses. Financial knowledge has increasingly received attention at the global level due to its critical role in poverty alleviation, entrepreneurship, and inclusive economic growth (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; Nogueira et al., 2025; Rehman & Mia, 2024).

The proliferation of microfinance institutions, mobile money services, and banking innovations in Sub-Saharan Africa has expanded the range of financial products available. However, a significant gap persists between access to financial services and their effective utilization. Inadequate financial knowledge impedes individuals from making informed financial choices, contributing to underutilization, debt mismanagement, and financial vulnerability. This is particularly true for women and young entrepreneurs in SMEs who face additional structural and educational barriers (Adeyombo et al., 2024; Aripin & Zuhriyah, 2025; Aristei et al., 2024; Asa et al., 2025).

The theory underlying the subject stems from human capital theory, which suggests that education, skills, and training increase the economic productivity of an individual (including their financial capability). It is also underpinned by behavioral economics theory, which critically assesses cognitive bias, imperfect information, and information asymmetry, and how they affect and influence financial decision-making. The latter approach is significant as it includes not just financial services but also interventions that help improve financial behavior and financial literacy, as well as capacity building.

Recent research also continues to establish a robust and significant association between financial knowledge and positive financial behaviors. Individuals with higher levels of financial knowledge are consistently more likely to engage in behaviors such as regular saving, budgeting, and prudent use of credit (Ameer & Khan, 2020; Grohmann, 2018; Kaiser & Lusardi, 2024; Morgan & Long, 2020; Morris et al., 2022; Rahman et al., 2021). In Africa, empirical evidence shows a positive impact of financial literacy on financial inclusion and financial stability (Duvenhage et al., 2025; Frimpong et al., 2022; Mabel, 2022; Mireku et al., 2023; Mugambe & Mulindwa, 2024; Sakanko et al., 2025). In Uganda, earlier research by Nanziri (2016) found that despite an increase in access to financial services, many people, particularly youth and women, were not sufficiently empowered or confident to effectively use these financial products. Recent empirical studies on the nexus between financial literacy and financial inclusion in Uganda (Ebong & George, 2021; Kasozi & Makina, 2021; Mpaata et al., 2020; Ogwang et al., 2024) confirm that women and youth are still disproportionately disadvantaged by the lack of financial knowledge and skills, even as access to formal and digital financial services improves.

Nonetheless, considerable controversy exists in this field. For example, a big question is how the relationships between product use and financial knowledge are directional, that is, does knowledge of financial products precede their use? In addition, which types of financial education are most effective, and is classroom-based training better than experiential training or digital interventions? Finally, critics have argued that measures of financial literacy can be improved and that poor financial decisions may be caused by other systemic factors that need to be addressed, such as poverty, gender inequality, and trust in institutions (Ansong et al., 2022; Birkenmaier et al., 2022; Caplan et al., 2018; Xiao & Huang, 2021).

New lines of research have also been informed by a focus on digital financial inclusion and the use of behavioral nudges in program design for financial education. Mobile technology, which has increased rapidly, especially in the African continent, has brought new opportunities and modalities to the delivery of financial services and training. In particular, technology has enabled the ability to make real-time and individualized interventions. (Abdul Mannan & Farhana, 2023; Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022; Sabbaghi, 2025; Simione, 2023). There is also randomized and field-based evidence to show the use of digital channels and behavioral nudges (SMS reminders, simplified choice architectures, etc.) can impact saving and mobile-money behavior, but not all nudges have proven effective (Andries & Walker, 2023; Chiwaula et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2020).

In this regard, the current study adds to this increasing stream of literature by looking at the effect of financial knowledge on the use of financial products among youth and women entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises in Uganda. Not only does the study consider levels of financial knowledge in important areas of business finance, such as loans, risk, and inflation, but it also provides a statistical test of the connection between financial knowledge and the use of financial products. This study's insights will help guide policy, training initiatives, and inclusive finance tactics aimed at underserved communities in emerging nations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1. Theoretical survey

There are multiple theories that explain the influence of financial knowledge on the use of financial products. For instance, the financial literacy theory of financial inclusion, introduced by Peterson K. Ozili, states that individuals with a higher level of financial knowledge are more likely to become active participants of the formal financial sector (Ozili, 2025). The fundamental premise of this theory is that educational initiatives enhancing citizens' financial literacy foster financial inclusion; as individuals attain financial literacy, they are more inclined to establish bank accounts and utilize formal financial services to enhance their well-being (Ozili, 2025). Financial literacy is considered a cost-effective national inclusion strategy because educating the public about money management and the available banking services heightens people's propensity to join the formal financial system (Ozili, 2025). However, it is important to note that this form of education only heightens awareness and willingness but does not provide individuals with the money they need to join formal finance. Even the most financially literate people can't join the formal finance system without enough money for transactions.

The vulnerable group theory of financial inclusion is another approach, introduced by Ozili. The idea behind it is that financial inclusion efforts and policies should focus on the needs of vulnerable groups in society that are most affected by economic downturns and shocks (Ozili, 2024). In other words, it states that the inclusion of vulnerable groups (such as the poor, youth, women, and the elderly) in the formal financial system will benefit them, as they will be able to access savings, credit, and other financial services that can improve their well-being and resilience (Ozili, 2024). One example of including vulnerable groups in the formal financial system is delivering government-to-person (G2P) welfare payments through formal bank accounts: digitized G2P transfers can benefit those in need and promote financial inclusion (particularly among women) as the unbanked would be incentivized to open accounts in order to receive these payments. Drawing on these principles, this study implemented a theory-of-change framework to connect interventions to outcomes (Weiss, 1995). By raising the financial literacy of young and female SME owners, the project would help them to use more formal financial products and, in turn, improve the financial performance and growth of their businesses.

2.2. Empirical survey

Financial knowledge is often mentioned as a precondition for financial inclusion. Atkinson and Messy (2013) point out that interventions that improve financial knowledge can help disadvantaged people access formal financial services and make more efficient use of financial products. Merely making financial services available to the poor is insufficient to fully bring them into the formal fold: access to formal financial services should be combined with the use of those services (Hidalgo-Mayorga et al., 2025). In fact, countries with low financial literacy levels also show a low degree of financial inclusion (Atkinson and Messy, 2013). This link is found again in recent research: a cross-country analysis finds that higher financial literacy is associated with a higher likelihood of accessing and using financial services, both in advanced and developing countries (Grohmann et al., 2017). An analysis focusing on Asian countries reveals that populations with higher literacy levels exhibit significantly better financial inclusion indicators (Le et al., 2019).

Financial knowledge also has a crucial role in maintaining good personal financial behavior. Lusardi (2008) discovered that those with low levels of financial literacy were significantly less likely to plan for retirement, to invest in the stock market, or to borrow responsibly (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). These findings have been supported by more recent research, which found that low literacy levels were linked to bad borrowing decisions (e.g., avoiding credit card fees) as well as other suboptimal behaviors (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Overall, education is also an essential determinant of financial health: more highly educated people are significantly more likely to have a bank account (Boel & Zimmerman, 2022). This link between education and financial inclusion has been demonstrated both in the US (e.g., lower years of education were associated with an increased likelihood of being unbanked (Boel & Zimmerman, 2022)) and globally, showing the need for financial knowledge as well as general education.

Cole et al. (2011) found that financial knowledge has been the most consistent predictor of the demand for financial services and that demand for financial services by the educated consumers leads to better financial decisions. Lyons and Kass-Hanna (2021) reported that vulnerable populations suffer financial exclusion, and a financially literate household saves money and doesn't borrow from informal sources.

Chikalipah (2017) affirmed illiteracy to be a barrier to financial inclusion in Sub-Saharan Africa on a data set of World Bank data on 20 SSA countries in 2014. Kodongo (2018) established through probit regression of cross-sectional household-level survey data, that financial literacy increases financial inclusion. Adetunji and David-West (2019), using a survey of 22,000 respondents, found that financial literacy has a significant effect on how people save through formal and informal financial institutions. Barugahara (2021) found financial illiteracy to be one of the barriers that hinder financial inclusion in Zimbabwe. Abel et al. (2018) confirmed through their study that financial literacy has a positive impact on financial inclusion in Zimbabwe. Evans (2018) and Oji (2015) argue that financial illiteracy is a significant challenge to inclusive finance in Africa. Financial literacy is an essential ingredient for inclusive finance because it promotes household practices of saving money, borrowing from money, investing resources, and taking insurance against financial emergencies.

Lyons et al. (2017) argue that financial knowledge, while a significant predictor of financial inclusion, may have a limited impact. Lyons et al. (2017) empirically assessed the impact of financial knowledge on loan demand among financially excluded Chinese households using the 2013 Chinese Household Finance Survey data and concluded that vulnerable populations are often unable to benefit from financial literacy training on the use of formal bank loans. The authors' study asserts that financial knowledge is a critical tool for financial inclusion, but economic and social barriers to financial access must be overcome before financial literacy programs can be effective. Infrastructure and social network externalities might be more crucial than financial knowledge. We must dismantle access barriers before financial knowledge can take effect. Gender, income, education, and age have been identified by Zins and Weill (2016) and Asuming et al. (2019) as the primary drivers of financial inclusion in Africa. Allen et al. (2014) and Evans (2018) found that innovation in financial services, along with internet and mobile phone use, were critical drivers of financial inclusion in Africa. The question is whether financial literacy is the best strategy to spur the use of financial products and services in Southwestern Uganda.

Okello Candiya Bongomin et al. (2017) analyzed how financial knowledge impacts financial inclusion for poor rural households in Uganda. In the study, financial inclusion of poor rural Ugandan households is shown through their financial knowledge, which is presented through their attitudes towards saving, borrowing, and insurance use. Behavioral financial knowledge does not impact financial inclusion for poor rural households in Uganda. The paper only looked at poor households that were in rural locations. The study only controlled for variables such as household income sources and location. The research did not account for some important demand- and supply-side factors that influence financial inclusion, including education, wealth, age, gender, and affordability, and may have omitted variable bias.

Kasozi and Makina (2021) find that financially literate individuals have a higher rate of financial inclusion in Uganda. The rates of financial inclusion revealed that male individuals are more financially included than females. The financial literacy measurement was also unique compared to the Okello Candiya Bongomin et al. (2017) method.

The researchers determined an individual's ability to handle finances well, plan for future welfare, and ability to access financial guidance with openness to technological solutions. The authors disregarded supply-side determinants to financial inclusion while focusing on the individual side alone. The study considered financial inclusion from the angle of holding an account. But there are other forms of financial inclusion, such as borrowing and investment.

Akileng et al. (2018) studied the determinants that had the most significant effect on the financial inclusion of Ugandan households. The study found that factors other than financial literacy and innovation had less influence on Ugandan household financial inclusion. The authors only assessed financial literacy and inclusion at an individual level when explaining how they were measured and controlled for only a subset of variables in the model. The authors employed an obscure methodology based on regression analysis.

2.3. Identified gaps

Current literature has not considered the influence of financial knowledge among SMEs on the uptake of financial products and services in Uganda. Current financial knowledge and financial inclusion studies in Uganda have focused only on individuals, not SMEs. Their measure of financial knowledge was not appropriate, and their measure of financial inclusion was too narrow. This study examined financial knowledge and the use of financial services among SMEs in Southwestern Uganda, specifically targeting young entrepreneurs and women entrepreneurs.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Efforts to improve financial inclusion in Uganda have focused on expanding microfinance services, mobile money, and digital financial solutions, but young people and women in Uganda, particularly those in small and medium enterprises (SMEs), tend to underutilize financial products and services. This underutilization is often linked to a lack of financial knowledge. There is evidence to show that there is a positive relationship between financial literacy and better financial behaviors and outcomes. People with a strong understanding of financial concepts are more likely to make informed financial decisions, leading to improved financial well-being. However, the link between the lack of knowledge and the underutilization of financial products in Uganda has been underexplored. While there is evidence to support the value of financial literacy in promoting positive financial behaviors and outcomes, a clear gap remains between the provision of financial services and their effective use. Filling this knowledge gap is important to help to achieve the goals of financial inclusion and empowering marginalized communities.

Tables

Table 1: Matrix for determining the sample size of SMEs

District	Target SMEs	Sample size	Sampling technique
Bushenyi	420	204	Random sampling
Kisoro	420	204	Random sampling
Total	840	408	Random sampling

Source: Authors' computations

Table 2: Reliability test results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.921	60

Source: Authors' computations

Table 3: Response rate for the questionnaire

District	Number of questionnaires administered	Returned	Return rate (%)
Bushenyi	204	200	98
Kisoro	204	195	95.6
Total	408	395	96.8

Source: Authors' computations (using primary data, 2023)

Table 4: Background characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	171	43.3
Female	224	56.7
Age bracket		
18-30	219	55.4
31-43	163	41.3
44-56	8	2
57+	5	1.3
Marital status		
Single	91	23.04
Married	245	62.03
Divorced	43	10.89
Widow	16	4.05
Level of education		
Primary	167	42.3
Secondary	132	33.4
Vocational training	47	11.9
Tertiary education	49	12.4
Religion		
Christian	329	83.3
Moslem	52	13.2
No religious affiliation	8	2
Others	6	1.5
Business location		
Urban	236	59.7
Rural	159	40.3
Business ownership		
Owner	344	87.1
Manager	51	12.9
Involvement in making decisions		
Yes	369	93.4
No	26	6.6

Source: Authors' computations (using primary data, 2023)

Table 5: Business financial knowledge

Assertion	False		True		Refused	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Profits are part of what your business pays to the bank to repay the loan	78	19.7	313	79.2	4	1
You use your business as collateral to obtain the loan	135	34.2	255	64.6	4	1
If the business is capable of making more money is likely to lose a lot of money	94	23.8	299	75.7	2	0.5
High prices means that the living conditions worsen	55	13.9	339	85.8	1	0.3
A short-term loan requires higher monthly payments than a long-term loan	95	24.1	295	74.7	5	1.3
Total interest paid on a short-term loan will be less than for a long term	109	27.6	281	71.1	5	1.3

Source: Authors' computations (using primary data, 2023)

Table 6: Financial product knowledge and utilization status

Product	Knowledge/ownership			Utilization	
	Response	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Account ownership	No	23	5.8	23	5.8
	Yes	372	94.2	372	94.2
Mobile money	No	18	4.6	41	10.4
	Yes	376	95.2	353	89.4
	Refused	1	0.3	1	0.3
ATM	No	110	27.8	115	29.1
	Yes	284	71.9	279	70.6
	Refused	1	0.3	1	0.3
Bank transfers	No	221	55.9	285	72.2
	Yes	173	43.8	109	27.6
	Refused	1	0.3	1	0.3
Business loan from the bank	No	103	26.1	140	35.4
	Yes	291	73.7	254	64.3
	Refused	1	0.3	1	0.3
SACCO	No	90	22.8	113	28.6
	Yes	304	77	281	71.1
	Refused	1	0.3	1	0.3

Source: Authors' computations (using primary data, 2023)

Table 7: Correlations between financial knowledge and financial product utilization

Variable		Financial knowledge	Financial product utilization
Pearson's	Financial knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	395
	Financial product utilization	Correlation Coefficient	.721**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	395

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Source: Authors' computations (using primary data, 2023)

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OR METHODS

4.1. Research design

The research employed cross-sectional and correlational designs to provide the research with an adequate general overview of the possible relationships between financial knowledge and the use of financial products. The use of the cross-sectional design was adequate because the time was used to collect the data from many respondents, and it was easy for the researcher to collect and study the prevailing patterns and trends as well as the correlations between the variables (Bryman, 2016).

4.2. Study area

This study was conducted in Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities, which are found in Southwestern Uganda, and they are among the country's fast-growing urban centers. Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities are two of Uganda's most rapidly growing commercial areas and are home to a large number of SMEs involved in manufacturing, retail trade, services, and agro-processing (Uganda Bureau of Statistics [UBOS], 2020). Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities were selected as the study area because of the vital role that SMEs play in the local economy. The local SMEs are involved in job creation, revenue generation, and community development. Small and medium-sized businesses in the two municipalities, particularly those owned and operated by women and the youth, face financial problems, particularly in terms of accessing and managing loan financing from formal banking institutions. Additionally, both

areas were picked because they are home to SMEs that actively use financial goods and products from commercial banks, microfinance organizations, SACCOs, and informal moneylenders. The existence of a variety of funding sources allows for the examination of the effect of the behavioral aspects of financial knowledge in a practical financial setting on the use of financial goods by SMEs.

4.3. Study population

The target population of this study was 420 SMEs per municipality, totaling 840 SMEs. The SMEs being studied operate in various sectors, including manufacturing industries, wholesale and retail trade, agro-processing, motor vehicle mechanics, metal works and fabrication, and services, creating a significant context for examining financial knowledge and the use of financial products.

4.4. Sample size and sampling technique

The study used a sample size of 408 respondents, consisting of 204 from each municipality. This sample was arrived at using the Yamane (1967) formula, which is commonly used to compute sample sizes based on known populations in social sciences research. With a target population of 840 SMEs, a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error were used to obtain this sample size. From each municipality, 204 SMEs were randomly selected from a list that was provided by the commercial officers. Then, for each SME, the manager or owner of the enterprise was randomly selected to fill out the questionnaire (see Table 1).

4.5. Data collection method

The study analyzed primary data. A structured questionnaire that was developed to make respondents respond to questions across outcome and independent variables was used to collect data. The structured questionnaire used standardized Likert-scale (Boone & Boone, 2012) items that are well-known and understood in reliability and behavioral and management research. It was used in the study to quantify attitudes, practices, and perceptions about financial knowledge and utilization of financial products among SME owners and managers.

The questionnaire assessed six crucial financial products: savings accounts, mobile money, Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs), bank transfers, bank loans, and SACCO loans. It also included extensive questions about details ranging from SME owner/manager demographics to financial activities such as money generation and expenditures, alongside cash flow analysis and risk management, as well as savings habits, borrowing tendencies, and payment methods, while assessing knowledge about financial products and providers. To ensure construct validity and consistency, survey items were taken from previous studies (Abel et al., 2018; Asuming et al., 2019; Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022) and modified to suit the SMEs' context in Kisoro and Bushenyi.

Before the actual data collection for the study, a pilot test was done in Kabale with 30 SMEs to assess the questionnaire's clarity, relevance, and internal consistency. The pilot feedback resulted in minor modifications to the language and order of items, thereby improving the instrument's face and content validity.

4.6. Measurement of variables

To ensure content validity and measurement consistency, the variables for this study were operationalized by using structured and validated questions modified from previously conducted empirical investigations (Abel et al., 2018; Asuming et al., 2019; Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022). The study investigated the role of financial knowledge on financial products utilization by women and youth-owned SMEs. In order to measure each of the constructs, financial products, financial knowledge, and product utilization, multiple indicators were utilized.

There were six essential components used to measure financial products: savings accounts, mobile money, Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), bank transfers, bank loans, and SACCO loans. Respondents were asked to indicate whether they used these financial products to measure financial product utilization. These financial inclusion

indicators were dummy variables representing the individual's use of a given financial product ($y = 1$, use of a given financial product; $y = 0$, otherwise).

The independent variable, financial knowledge, was measured using the SME owner's ability to make informed borrowing choices and their understanding of basic financial product principles. The construct included several knowledge-based indicators. These indicators included questions on the topics of interest calculations, amortization schedules, credit assessments, and loan term evaluations. With this multidimensional measurement of financial knowledge, the research was able to assess how the degree of business financial literacy relates to the use of financial products.

4.7. Reliability

To determine whether the instrument has a degree of reliability, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used. The coefficient is an established method of determining internal consistency (Kothari, 2004). This process was completed so as to determine whether the instrument produced consistent results. Cronbach's alpha is measured on a scale of 0-1. The higher the alpha value, the more the items being measured are consistent. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher is typically needed to establish an instrument as having been shown to be reliable (Taber, 2018). Table 2 shows the results of the reliability test.

4.8. Data analysis

The collected data were then analyzed using both descriptive and correlational statistics. This research sought to explore the relationship between financial knowledge and the use of financial products by women- and youth-owned SMEs in Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities, Southwestern Uganda. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

Descriptive statistics were generated to provide a summary of the background information and general characteristics of the respondents. In this study, the descriptive statistics collected relevant information on the owners and managers of SMEs. The information was collected on the owner's gender, age category, marital status, level of education, business age, location, and religion. Frequencies and percentages were used to present these background characteristics of the respondents. The result of this presented a clear picture of the SME respondents and their business environment.

After the descriptive analysis, a financial product utilization index constructed using principal component analysis to capture the use of financial products was conducted. Individual financial inclusion/financial product utilization indicators would provide less information than the index created by the indicators using principal component analysis. The principal component analysis incorporated the unique characteristics of each indicator into one index and, therefore, tends to provide more useful insights and, as a result, more reliable outcomes than separate indicators. The primary inferential analysis was conducted using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator.

4.9. Ethical considerations

The research followed the ethical standards related to studies involving human participants in the field of financial behavior and decision-making processes in SMEs. The study considered the sensitivity of information regarding financial knowledge and the use of financial products, and we employed appropriate measures of caution to uphold the research's integrity, transparency, and the respondents' rights.

Ethical approval was sought before the actual data collection from the Kabale University Research Ethics Committee (KAB-REC), and approval was granted with KAB-REC number PI002/5/2022-2023. Approval and official recognition from the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) with registration number SS2660ES were sought and obtained. The above approval gave the researchers the right to interview the SME owners/managers in Kisoro and Bushenyi Municipalities for this study.

The participation of the study subjects was voluntary. The nature and purpose of the study were explained to all

the respondents. The respondents were given a written informed consent form, which describes their rights as subjects, such as the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw at any time without penalty or reprisal.

The respondents' identities were protected by not recording their personal information, such as names, business registration numbers, and contact numbers, in the dataset. The collected data were used solely for research purposes, with all responses remaining confidential and available only to the researchers.

Additionally, there were efforts to minimize risks for participants. The questionnaire was not sensitive or intrusive. The questions dealt only with financial practices in a business environment. The questions were not beyond the scope of the study and did not injure or cause pain for the participants.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Data analysis

This section reports research findings on the influence of financial knowledge on the use of financial products by youth and women in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the Kisoro and Bushenyi districts of southwest Uganda. The first subsection offers some basic facts (descriptive statistics) about the respondents, while the next subsection discusses the findings.

5.1.1. Response rate

Response rate refers to the percentage of respondents who completed the questionnaire and returned it to all respondents (Taherdoost & Madanchian, 2024). It was required to divide the number of returned questionnaires by the number of provided questionnaires for each respondent's class to calculate a response rate, and after this division, the number is multiplied by 100. Table 3 indicates the response rate. Table 3 shows that the total number of distributed questionnaires was 408, the number of full responses was 395, and the return rate was concluded to be 96.8%. Booker et al. (2021) argue that the research can draw a valid conclusion if its response rate is higher than 80%. The return rate of 96.8% shows the high number of respondents who were engaged in this study.

5.1.2. Descriptive statistics

This section presents the demographic and background characteristics of the 395 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) respondents who took part in the study. It was important to find out from the respondents their age, gender, marital status, education levels, religion, location of the business, management of the business, and their involvement in decision-making. These specific characteristics would have an effect on financial product utilization. Such information helped to draw explanations and conclusions from findings as presented below. Table 4 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the characteristics of the respondents in question.

The composition of males and females is 43.3% and 56.7%, respectively. The number of women participating in the study was larger than the number of men, but the disproportion is small enough to say that in the research, both sexes were well represented, and the gender gap in the use of financial products in SMEs is narrowing. The largest number of respondents fall into the age group 18-30 years (55.4%), followed by the 31-43 age group (41.3%). The number of people of 44-56 years and above 56 years is significantly lower (2% and 1.3%, respectively). In this case, we can say that the research covered young and energetic entrepreneurs.

The highest percentage of respondents were married people at 62%, while singles formed the second largest group at 23%. Divorced and widowed were 10.9% and 4.1%, respectively. This illustrates that the businesses were run by stable families (married people) and that women, men, and children had a high tendency of sharing their labor. In the educational sector, the majority of the respondents had a primary level of education at 42.3%. Secondary and tertiary had 33.4% and 12.4%, respectively. The remaining 11.9% had received vocational training. In the religious sphere, Christians had the largest proportion of respondents at 83.3%, while Moslems had 13.2%. The "non-religious" respondents and those in the "others" category had low percentages of 8% and 6%, respectively.

The study established that the sampled businesses were from urban areas and rural areas in the percentages of 59.7% and 40.3%, respectively. It means that businesses sampled were mainly from urbanized areas. The table also indicates that 87.1% of the respondents were owners of the sampled businesses and 12.9% of the respondents were employees/managers of the sampled businesses. The way the respondents are presented shows that the majority of small and medium enterprises were individually owned, and people are in business as a form of employment. The majority of the respondents, 93.4%, participated in financial decision-making, while the minority, 6.6%, did not.

5.1.3. Financial knowledge

This section looks at the financial knowledge of respondents about financing of business, managing risks, and insurance of the business. It also addresses findings about the planning of business as well as external factors that determine the operation of the business. The findings are presented in Table 5. The table indicates that the majority, 79.2% of respondents, used profits from their business to repay a bank loan. Only 19.7% of respondents disagreed that profits were part of what their businesses used to repay bank loans, and 1% were undecided. This implies that business people should use bank loans for the intended purpose, not diverting funds, since profits are part of the amount used to back the loan. 64.6% of respondents agreed that their businesses were used as collateral to obtain bank loans, while a minority of respondents (34.2%) refused the statement that business people used their business as collateral security. This implies that big businesses enjoyed financial economies of scale. This implies that financial knowledge was important to individuals when trying to access loans from the banks, to understand all the requirements.

Majority 75.7% of respondents, agreed that the business that was able to make a lot of money had high chances of losing it, while 23.8% of respondents did not understand the scenario of this risk aversion. This confirms that most business people understood the risks involved in business and had tried to insure their business in preparation for future uncertainties. 85.8% of respondents agreed that high prices meant that the living conditions worsened, compared to 13.9% who disagreed that high prices worsened living conditions. This implies that high commodity prices (inflation) made the cost of doing business high.

The majority of the respondents 74.7% agreed that a short-term loan required higher monthly payments than a long-term loan, while the minority 24.1% disagreed that short term loan required higher monthly payments. This shows that business people had the capacity to plan beyond a short-term period. In addition, 71.1% of respondents knew that the total interest paid on a short-term loan would be less than that of a long-term loan. This indicates the financial knowledge that people had about financial products and services.

5.1.4. Financial product utilization status

This section presents findings on financial products awareness and utilization. The responses are tabulated in Table 6. The table shows that the majority, 94.2% of respondents, owned accounts in the bank or mobile phone and other financial institutions, while 5.8% of respondents had no account for their businesses. This implied that most business operators used financial products to keep money and carry out transactions. The majority of respondents, 95.2%, said they had heard about mobile money, and 89.4% had used it in their business in the last 24 months, while 5.8% of respondents had not heard about the mobile money service.

The majority of respondents, 77% and 73.7%, had heard about business loans and the use of Sacco as an electronic payment method, respectively. This also presented the findings that 64.3% and 71.1% have used business loans from the bank and obtained services from the Sacco in the last 24 months, respectively. This indicated that business people used financial products and services for the growth of their businesses. However, the majority of respondents, 72.2%, did not use bank transfers as one of the methods of electronic payments. This might be due to low financial literacy since it involved a lot of understanding of documents compared to mobile money, ATM and SACCOs.

5.1.5. Hypothesis testing

The researcher performed a correlation analysis to study how financial knowledge correlates with financial product utilization based on these hypotheses.

Null hypothesis (H_0): The level of financial understanding does not significantly relate to how people use financial products.

Alternative hypothesis (H_1): The level of financial understanding relates to how individuals use financial products.

Table 7 presents the results of the Pearson correlation analysis. The correlation coefficient value of 0.721 confirmed the existence of a positive correlation between financial knowledge and financial product utilization. This was statistically significant at 1%. This result suggests that financial knowledge significantly enhances the utilization of financial products among youth and women in SMEs.

5.2. Discussion

This section examined the financial knowledge levels of young entrepreneurs and women business owners in SMEs. The study assessed financial knowledge by examining business ownership status, educational attainment, participation in financial decision-making, and comprehension of financial concepts. A majority of SMEs, 87.1%, operated under owner management, while 12.9% featured separate ownership and management. The findings matched Pipreka's (2009) claim that financially knowledgeable entrepreneurs tend to make informed financial decisions and establish confident relationships with financial service providers to obtain preferred financial services. According to data collected from participants, 93.4% reported that they participated in financial decision-making activities. The majority of youth and women SME owners took responsibility for their business financial management. The results of this research confirmed Lusardi and Mitchell's (2014) argument that financial literacy leads individuals to engage actively in financial management and make superior financial decisions.

The research indicated that primary education was completed by 42.3% of participants, while only 12.4% reached tertiary education levels. The low levels of education appeared to restrict individuals' ability to develop financial literacy skills. The FinScope (2018) discovered that many Ugandan adults lacked secondary education, which contributed to their exclusion from financial systems. Alqam and Hamshari (2024) discovered that people with lower educational attainment had reduced financial knowledge, which limited their ability to access financial services effectively. management and making superior financial decisions.

The data showed that 79.2% of participants chose to use their profits to settle their loans, which demonstrated their understanding of debt responsibilities. Lyons et al. (2017) found that financially literate businesspeople understood loan repayment's critical role in maintaining creditworthiness. The research revealed that 64.6% of SMEs put their business assets forward as loan collateral, which represented their financial planning strategies. Kasozi and Makina (2021) established that enterprises with financial acumen typically utilize their assets as leverage for growth.

The strong positive relationship between financial knowledge and financial product utilization ($R = 0.721, p < 0.01$) indicates that individuals with higher levels of financial knowledge are significantly more likely to access and actively use formal financial products such as savings accounts, credit facilities, insurance, and digital financial services. The magnitude of the correlation suggests not merely a marginal association but a substantial linkage, implying that financial knowledge is a central driver of effective participation in the financial system.

This finding aligns closely with Lusardi and Tufano (2015), who argue that financial literacy enhances individuals' capacity to make informed financial decisions, particularly in complex financial environments. Financially knowledgeable individuals are better able to evaluate the costs and benefits of different financial products, understand contractual terms such as interest rates, fees, and repayment schedules, and assess risks associated with borrowing and investment. As a result, they are less likely to be excluded from formal financial markets due to fear, misinformation, or mistrust, and more likely to select products that match their financial needs and constraints.

Moreover, the strength of the relationship implies that financial knowledge reduces behavioral barriers to financial inclusion. Limited financial literacy has been shown to exacerbate problems such as over-indebtedness, under-saving, and avoidance of formal financial institutions. In contrast, increased financial knowledge builds confidence and self-efficacy, encouraging individuals to engage with a broader range of financial services.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The results underscore the need for context-specific financial literacy initiatives targeted at rural women and youth entrepreneurs to empower them to make informed financial decisions. With the increasing penetration of mobile technology, policymakers and financial service providers can leverage digital platforms to deliver financial education content in real-time and at scale with minimal costs. Banks and microfinance institutions should consider integrating financial literacy modules into their client onboarding processes to enhance loan repayment behavior and customer satisfaction. Embedding practical financial education in vocational training and secondary school curricula could facilitate early acquisition of financial skills.

7. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

7.1. Contributions to the scientific community

The study makes a contribution to the emerging evidence base from developing countries that is increasingly associating financial literacy with financial product use. This work is particularly important for the youth and women populations, where evidence from sub-Saharan Africa is limited. The study also bridges the two leading theoretical perspectives by explicating behavior using human capital theory and behavioral economics.

7.2. Future research

Conduct longitudinal studies to track changes in financial literacy over time and determine if increased knowledge translates to sustained behavior change. Perform randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to evaluate the impact of different financial education delivery methods (e.g., digital vs. in-person classroom). Expand the research to multiple regions in Uganda or compare results across East African countries to improve generalizability. Analyze the differences in financial behavior between male and female entrepreneurs, rural and urban SMEs, or educated and non-educated participants for more targeted interventions. Future research can also explore the impact of digital financial literacy (distinct from traditional financial knowledge) on the adoption and responsible use of mobile banking and fintech services.

8. CONCLUSION

This study was designed to test the hypothesis that financial knowledge relates to financial product use among youth and women entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) operating in the Southwestern Municipalities of Bushenyi and Kisoro in Uganda. The study, which used quantitative methods to gather and analyze the data, found a strong, statistically significant positive relationship between financial knowledge and use of formal financial services. More specifically, this research has found that financial knowledge in areas such as loan management, risk perception, and inflation awareness significantly improves the responsible and effective use of financial products. This finding reinforces the notion that expanding financial literacy efforts will provide financial services and resources to the unbanked, particularly those who are currently excluded. This study further highlights the importance of integrating financial education into the mainstream of financial inclusion efforts to promote long-term sustainable financial practices and empowerment for the youth and women.

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ORCID

Faustino Byanyima Byanyima <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7232-5584>

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